

Preventing, Avoiding and Mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gears and associated marine litter

PREVENT

marine litter derived from fisheries activities

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

AVOID

loss of fishing gears

Fishing Gears Location with Acoustic Tags

MITIGATE

harmful impacts of ALDFG

Detection and Removal of ALDFG

WORKING DIRECTLY WITH THE FISHING INDUSTRY

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